

Socio-Economic Impact of Education on Urban Women in Pakistan

Sarwat Qayyum^a

^a V-Principal Govt Grammar School and College Swabi, KPK Pakistan

Abstract

Education is a word has been derived from Latin word "Educare", means to train. Therefore, the harmonious growth of the potentialities for achieving the qualities desirable and useful in the human society is called education. It is claimed that by educating women we can develop our economy, family health and decrease population growth.

1. Aim

To explore the socio-economic impact of education on urban women.

2. Material and methods

A prospective study design was used. Over a period of six months 50 respondents were randomly selected from Hayat Abad, an urban city in the North West of Pakistan. A questionnaire was used to explore marital, educational, occupational, social, economical and political status of urban women.

3. Results

Of the total, 50% (25) were employed, where 56% were married and 44% unmarried. Of the employed participants, 56% were teachers followed by social worker 16%. Monthly income was significantly high ($p=001$) of women with master degree. Understanding between wife and husband was also very significant in women with masters. . 78% of employed women replied that Parda (Hija) should be on choice not imposed. 52% of educated women replied participation in social activates, such as parties, shopping etc.

4. Conclusions

Education has a high impact on urban women because it is directly related to employment, decision of power, economy and social life. Urban women with high education have significant political awareness and empowerment. Improving women educational level in rural areas of Pakistan is the key for economic growth and political empowerment

May 9, 2019

5. Keywords

Women, Education, Socio-economic, Urban, Peshawar, Pakistan